

7E's LEARNING MODEL IN TEACHING KINEMATICS FOR SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STEM

Ric Jay Tingzon Laceda, MAT ¹, Rezy Villegas-Mendoza, Ph.D. ²

¹ *Senior High School Department, Eastern Visayas Regional Science High School, Catbalogan City, Samar, Philippines*

² *College of Arts and Sciences, Samar State University, Catbalogan City, Samar, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15034388>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness of the 7E's Learning Model in improving senior high school students' conceptual understanding of Kinematics. Despite the critical role of STEM education, Filipino students struggle with physics, particularly kinematics, as shown by their poor performance in international assessments. Addressing this challenge requires innovative instructional approaches, yet research on the 7E's Learning Model in senior high school physics remains limited. A quasi-experimental nonequivalent groups design was used, involving two Grade 12 classes from Eastern Visayas Regional Science High School. The experimental group (n=33) received instruction using the 7E's Learning Model, while the control group (n=33) was taught through traditional lecture-based methods. A standardized physics concept test in Kinematics was adapted to assess students' conceptual understanding before and after the intervention. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and t-tests for dependent and independent samples. Results revealed that students exposed to the 7E's Learning Model had a significantly higher mean gain of 11.52 compared to 6.6 in the control group, with statistical analyses confirming a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in their learning gains. The findings suggest that the 7E's Learning Model fosters a better conceptual understanding of Kinematics. The study also identified uniformly accelerated motion, projectile motion, and uniform circular motion as the least learned competencies, leading to the development of a detailed lesson plan integrating the 7E's model. This study underscores the importance of student-centered approaches in physics instruction and recommends its broader application in STEM education to enhance learning outcomes.

Keywords: *7E's Learning Model, conceptual understanding, Kinematics, physics instruction, STEM education*

INTRODUCTION

Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education is essential for preparing individuals to solve complex problems, drive innovation, and support economic growth. It equips learners with the necessary skills for modern challenges and contributes to national development (Kormakova et al., 2023; Richner, 2023). UNESCO emphasizes that science education fosters critical thinking, curiosity, and an understanding of the natural world, making it crucial for sustainable progress (Ayeni, 2021).

In the Philippines, the K-12 curriculum was introduced to enhance science education through a holistic approach, progressively integrating scientific concepts across grade levels. This curriculum prioritizes hands-on exploration and inquiry-based learning to develop critical thinking and scientific literacy (Sadera et al., 2020). Its primary goal is to produce informed citizens who can apply scientific knowledge in everyday life and make sound decisions based on scientific principles.

Despite these efforts, Filipino students continue to perform poorly in international assessments such as the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), reflecting low scientific literacy compared to their global peers (Bernardo et al., 2023; Cordova & Linaugo, 2022). The Philippines consistently ranks among the lowest-performing nations, showing minimal improvement over time (Department of Education, 2019). This persistent underperformance highlights the urgent need for more effective teaching strategies to enhance students' scientific understanding and academic performance.

Physics education, a fundamental component of STEM, plays a key role in developing students' analytical and reasoning skills. However, many students struggle with physics concepts, particularly Kinematics, which is crucial in understanding motion (Amin et al., 2020; Sundari, 2023). Studies show that misconceptions and a lack of conceptual understanding hinder students' mastery of Kinematics, leading to challenges at both high school and college levels (Mufit et al., 2022; Rahmadani, 2023). These difficulties contribute to low retention rates and poor problem-solving abilities among students.

Kinematics is identified as one of the least learned competencies among senior high school students in the Philippines (Cornejo, 2022). Students often face difficulties interpreting kinematic graphs, linking them to physical concepts, and applying equations to real-world situations. These struggles are further exacerbated by a lack of interest, uninspiring instructional materials, and ineffective teaching methods (Mbwile & Ntivuguruzwa, 2023; Zavala et al., 2017). Addressing these challenges requires

innovative, student-centered teaching approaches that actively engage learners in the learning process.

One such approach is the 7E's Learning Model, a constructivist-based strategy that promotes active engagement through seven phases: elicit, engage, explore, explain, elaborate, evaluate, and extend (Bektiarso, 2023; Iksan et al., 2018). While extensively studied in elementary and middle school settings, research on its application in senior high school STEM education, particularly in Kinematics, remains limited (Aliyu et al., 2022; Maskur et al., 2019; Marfilinda et al., 2020). This study examined the impact of the 7E's Learning Model on senior high school students' learning performance in Kinematics, aiming to provide insights for educators and curriculum developers in improving physics instruction and overall student achievement.

Research Objectives

This study developed a detailed learning plan for the Kinematics of STEM students using the 7E's Learning Model. Specifically, it aimed to:

1. Determine the level of conceptual understanding of the two groups of respondents in Kinematics in terms of their:
 - 1.1 pretest mean scores;
 - 1.2 posttest mean scores.
2. Determine the significant difference in the pretest and posttest mean scores of the two groups of respondents.
3. Determine the significant difference in the mean gain score of the two groups of respondents.
4. Develop a detailed learning plan based on the least learned competencies for Kinematics emphasizing the 7E's Learning Model.

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses of the study were tested:

1. There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the two groups of respondents in Kinematics.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean gain scores of the two groups of respondents in Kinematics.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at Eastern Visayas Regional Science High School (EVRSHS) in Catbalogan City, Philippines, focusing on Grade 12 STEM students during the 2024–2025 school year. The study employed a quasi-experimental nonequivalent

groups design, where two intact classes were selected using a coin toss to determine the experimental (33 students) and control groups (33 students). The experimental group received instruction using the 7E's Learning Model, while the control group was taught using traditional lecture-based instruction. The study was limited to Kinematics and focused on students who had no more than two absences during the experiment to ensure consistency in learning.

A standardized physics concept test adapted from Ole & Gallos (2021) was used to assess students' understanding of Kinematics. To confirm its suitability for the current study's context, the test underwent pilot testing and validation using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), yielding a reliability score of 0.805, ensuring internal consistency. The pretest was administered to establish baseline knowledge, followed by a 10-day instructional phase, after which the posttest, identical to the pretest, was conducted to measure learning gains. Attendance records were monitored throughout the study.

The collected data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to measure performance, while t-tests for dependent and independent samples determined statistical significance between pretest and posttest scores. An item analysis was conducted to identify the least learned competencies in Kinematics, such as uniformly accelerated motion, projectile motion, and circular motion. The results were used to develop a detailed lesson plan integrating the 7E's Learning Model to enhance students' conceptual understanding and engagement in physics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Conceptual Understanding of the Two Groups of Respondents in Kinematics

Table 1 presents the comparative data on the level of conceptual understanding of the controlled and experimental groups in the pretest and posttest assessments.

As shown in Table 1, The controlled group scored a pretest mean of 8.64, which has a corresponding grade of 67 and falls under the Below 75: Did Not Meet Expectations level according to the DepEd grading scale (Deped Order No. 8, s. 2015-Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 BEP). This indicates that the students in the controlled group had a poor initial understanding of kinematics concepts prior to instruction. The experimental group, on the other hand, scored a slightly higher pretest mean of 10.03, which has a corresponding grade of 68, which also falls under the Below 75: Did Not Meet Expectations category.

Like the control group, the experimental group demonstrated a low initial understanding of the subject matter. Both groups started with limited knowledge and understanding of Kinematics as they gained scores lower than fifty percent of the total

test score, suggesting that additional instructional intervention was necessary to improve their learning performance.

Furthermore, the control group achieved a posttest mean score of 15.24 with a corresponding grade of 73 and still falls under the Below 75: Did Not Meet Expectations level. Although there was an improvement from the pretest, the level of learning performance remained below satisfactory. On the other hand, the experimental group achieved a posttest mean score of 21.55, with a corresponding grade of 83, which falls under the 80-84: Satisfactory level.

Table 1
Conceptual Understanding of Students in terms of their Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores

Group	n	Pretest			Post Test		
		Mean	Grade	Description	Mean	Grade	Description
Controlled	33	8.64	67	<i>Did Not Meet Expectations</i>	15.24	73	<i>Did Not Meet Expectations</i>
Experimental	33	10.03	68	<i>Did Not Meet Expectations</i>	21.55	83	<i>Satisfactory</i>

Legend: 90-100: Outstanding, 85-89: Very Satisfactory, 80-84: Satisfactory, 75-79: Fairly Satisfactory, Below 75: Did Not Meet Expectations (DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015).

This indicates a significant improvement in the level of learning performance, demonstrating a satisfactory grasp of kinematics concepts after instruction. This aligns with the findings of Aliyu et al. (2022), which highlighted that the 7E learning model is linked to enhanced success and achievement in science education by providing students with opportunities to explore and understand concepts effectively. The findings are supported by the work of Hairini (2024), who found that inquiry-based learning strategies significantly enhance students' problem-solving skills and overall academic achievement in physics. The study emphasized that methods like the 7E's Learning Model provide a structured framework for addressing misconceptions and fostering meaningful learning, as evidenced by the experimental group's transition from "Did Not Meet Expectations" to "Satisfactory" in the present study.

The current study's findings also support the study conducted by Dervić et al. (2018) on the abstract nature of kinematics concepts, such as instantaneous velocity and acceleration, which further emphasizes the topic's inherent difficulty. Their study found that even with innovative instructional methods, students often require extended practice and reinforcement to achieve mastery. These challenges align with the current study's findings, where despite significant improvement, the experimental group showed only a modest increase in their posttest scores.

Building upon the analysis of students' conceptual understanding in kinematics based on pretest and posttest results, Table 2 highlights the least learned competencies in the subject. These findings offer additional insights into specific areas where students encountered difficulties.

Table 2
Least Learned Competencies in Kinematics

Topic	Most Essential Learning Competency (MELC)	Average % of Correct Response	Remarks
Uniformly Accelerated Linear Motion	a) Convert a verbal description of a physical situation involving uniform acceleration in one dimension into a mathematical description (<i>STEM_GP12Kin-Ib-12</i>)	66	Average Mastery
Projectile Motion	b) Calculate range, time of flight, and maximum heights of projectiles. (<i>STEM_GP12KIN-Ic-23</i>)	66	Average Mastery
Circular Motion	c) Infer quantities associated with circular motion such as tangential velocity, centripetal acceleration, tangential acceleration, radius of curvature (<i>STEM_GP12KIN-Ic-26</i>)	70	Moderately Average Mastery

As shown in Table 2, mastery levels for the least learned competencies range from 66% to 70%, categorized as "Average Mastery" or "Moderately Average Mastery." Despite these remarks, the mastery levels for all competencies fall below the passing percentage of 75%, indicating a need for significant improvement. In Uniform Accelerated Motion, students demonstrated difficulty converting verbal descriptions of physical situations into mathematical representations, achieving a mastery level of 66%. This aligns with the findings by Nizaruddin et al. (2017), who noted that students often struggle to connect real-world scenarios with abstract mathematical models.

Similarly, in Projectile Motion, students demonstrated only 66% mastery, reflecting difficulties in applying equations to calculate range, time of flight, and maximum height. Hidayatulloh et al. (2021) found that many students struggle to understand the relationship between the angle of projection and the distance traveled, leading to persistent misconceptions. Additionally, Boller-Aying and Villegas-Mendoza (2024) noted that while students may grasp the theoretical concepts, they often face challenges in practical applications due to misconceptions about the independence of horizontal and vertical motion, difficulties with kinematic equations, and visualization issues related to launch angle, initial velocity, and gravity. Their study suggests that integrating project-based learning and interactive simulations can enhance conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills by providing hands-on experiences and real-world applications.

Meanwhile, in Circular Motion, students achieved a mastery level of 70%, indicating struggles with concepts such as centripetal acceleration and tangential velocity. Kotvytska and Ješková (2024) observed that many students confuse centripetal and centrifugal forces, highlighting the need for clearer explanations and practical applications. Although these mastery levels reflect some understanding, they fall short of the passing standard of 75%, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to bridge these learning gaps.

Difference in the Pretest and Post Test Mean Scores Between Experimental and Control Groups

Table 3 compares the pretest and posttest mean scores for the controlled and experimental groups.

As Table 3 shows, the controlled group had a pretest mean score of 8.64 and a posttest mean score of 15.24, resulting in a mean gain of 6.6. The statistical analysis yielded a t-value of 9.122 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a significant difference at the 0.05 level. This result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, suggesting a significant improvement in the controlled group's performance.

Similarly, the experimental group showed a pretest mean score of 10.03 and a posttest mean score of 21.55, with a mean gain of 11.52. The corresponding t-value was 13.501, and the p-value was 0.000, also indicating a significant difference at the 0.05 level. As with the controlled group, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming a statistically significant improvement in the experimental group's performance.

Table 3**Comparison of the Pretest and Post-test Mean Scores of the Students**

Group	Means		Difference	t	p-value	Interpretation
	Pre-Test	Post Test				
Controlled	8.64	15.24	6.60	9.122	0.000	S/Reject Ho
Experimental	10.03	21.55	11.52	13.501	0.000	S/Reject Ho

Level of Significance is at 0.05, two-tailed

Both groups demonstrated significant progress from the pretest to the posttest. However, the experimental group achieved a higher mean gain compared to the control group, suggesting that the intervention applied to the experimental group was more effective in enhancing their performance. The findings of this study align with the research conducted by Maskur et al. (2019), which highlighted that those students taught using the 7E's Learning Model demonstrated significantly greater gains in physics concepts, such as heat and temperature, compared to those taught using traditional lecture-based methods.

Difference in Mean Gain Scores Between the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 4 presents the t-test results for independent sample analysis of the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups.

Table 4**Comparison of the Mean Gain Scores Between the Control Group and Experimental Group**

Group	Mean Gain Score	Difference	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Controlled	6.60				
Experimental	11.52	4.92	-4.387	.000	S/Reject Ho

Level of Significance is at 0.05, two-tail, df = 64

The independent samples t-test results ($t=-4.387$, $df=64$, $p=0.000$) revealed a statistically significant difference in gain scores between the control and experimental groups. The negative t-value indicates that the mean gain score of the control group was lower than that of the experimental group. On average, students in the experimental group outperformed their peers in the control group by approximately 4.92 points. The null hypothesis (H_0), which posited no significant difference in gain scores between the

groups, was rejected, as the p-value of 0.000 is less than the significance level of 0.05. This confirms that the observed difference is statistically significant and unlikely to be due to chance.

These findings demonstrate that the experimental group, which utilized the 7E's Learning Model, achieved significantly higher gain scores than the control group. The results suggest that the innovative instructional approach had a positive impact on student's learning outcomes, enhancing both comprehension and retention of the subject matter. The significant improvement in gain scores supports the effectiveness of the 7E's Learning Model as a valuable tool for improving student achievement in Kinematics, particularly when compared to traditional teaching methods. This is congruent with the study of Saraç & Tarhan (2017), which stated that the 7E learning cycle can lead to more meaningful learning experiences and better student performance.

Integration of 7Es Learning Model in Lesson Plan for the Least Learned Competencies in Kinematics

Table 5 provides a clear and organized overview of how the 7E's Learning Model is systematically applied to teaching three least learned competencies/topics in Kinematics: uniformly accelerated motion, projectile motion, and circular motion. Each phase of the model is tailored to enhance student engagement, deepen understanding, and promote the application of concepts in real-world contexts. The appended developed detailed lesson plan for Kinematics shows such integration of the innovative learning model.

The integration of the 7E's Learning Model into the lesson plan for Kinematics aligns well with research-supported teaching practices, enhancing both student engagement and learning outcomes.

Table 5
Integration of 7Es Learning Model in Lesson Plan for the Least Learned Competencies in Kinematics

Least Learned Competencies/Topics in Kinematics	The Phase of 7E's Learning Model	Integration in the Lesson Plan
Uniformly Accelerated Motion	Elicit	Ask students to recall what they know about motion and acceleration.

Engage	Show a real-life video of a car accelerating and decelerating, sparking curiosity and discussion about motion.
Explore	Guide students through an experiment using a ramp and a toy car to measure distances and times for different inclinations.
Explain	Facilitate a discussion on the relationships between displacement, velocity, and acceleration using graphs and equations.
Elaborate	Assign problems involving uniformly accelerated motion for students to solve in groups.
Evaluate	Administer a post-activity quiz to measure understanding of concepts like equations of motion and acceleration.
Extend	Ask students to research real-life applications of uniformly accelerated motion, such as in roller coasters or vehicles.

Projectile Motion

Elicit	Pose questions to students about objects thrown into the air, identifying misconceptions about horizontal and vertical motions.
Engage	Demonstrate a simple projectile motion using a ball, asking students to predict its trajectory.
Explore	Provide students with simulations to calculate the range, height, and time of flight of a projectile launched at different angles.
Explain	Explain the independence of horizontal and vertical motions using diagrams and equations.

		<p>Elaborate Give students real-world problems, such as calculating the optimum angle for a basketball shot, to apply learned concepts.</p> <p>Evaluate Conduct a formative assessment using problem-solving tasks related to projectile motion.</p> <p>Extend Challenge students to analyze the motion of fireworks or sports like football and report their findings.</p>
Uniform Motion	Circular	<p>Elicit Ask students to share observations of objects in circular motion, such as a car turning around a curve, a planet orbiting around the sun, or a ball attached to a string and swung in a circle.</p> <p>Engage Show a video of a roller coaster loop or a car taking a sharp turn, prompting discussions about forces acting on the object.</p> <p>Explore Provide a lab activity where students measure the radius of the circle, the time for one complete revolution, and the speed of the object in circular motion.</p> <p>Explain Discuss the concepts of centripetal force, tangential velocity, and acceleration, supported by equations and examples.</p> <p>Elaborate Assign group activities to solve problems involving circular motion, such as calculating the speed of a satellite in orbit.</p> <p>Evaluate Test understanding through a short quiz or worksheet focusing on the application of circular motion concepts.</p>

Extend	Ask students to research and present how circular motion is applied in engineering, such as in centrifuges or flywheels.
--------	--

The table shows that the Elicit phase activates prior knowledge through diagnostic quizzes, which uncover students' existing ideas and misconceptions. According to Pires et al. (2020) and Kesteren et al. (2018), activating prior knowledge is crucial for helping students build a framework for new information and integrate it with existing knowledge, facilitating deeper understanding.

In the Engage phase, the teacher sparks curiosity by demonstrating kinematics concepts. As Cents-Boonstra et al. (2020) emphasize, lessons that begin with high levels of enthusiasm and student activation tend to be more engaging. This phase ensures that students are mentally and emotionally prepared to explore new concepts.

During the Explore phase, students conduct hands-on experiments, such as working with inclined planes, to investigate kinematics principles. Facilitating active exploration helps students construct their understanding, as highlighted by Pasju et al. (2022). Teachers guide students during this phase, ensuring their exploration remains focused and productive.

In the Explain phase, students analyze their experimental findings and connect them to formal kinematics concepts. Providing opportunities for students to articulate their understanding enables teachers to identify and address any gaps or misconceptions (Libata et al., 2022). Additional clarifications from the teacher further deepen students' comprehension of concepts like displacement and velocity.

The Elaborate phase extends learning by challenging students to apply their knowledge to real-world problems, such as calculating projectile motion. This approach, supported by Maskur et al. (2019), develops critical thinking skills and reinforces students' ability to transfer knowledge to new contexts.

In the Evaluate phase, post-lesson quizzes and reflective questions are used to assess students' mastery of Kinematics. Shesilya and Aloysius (2023) highlight the importance of using formative and summative assessments to identify misconceptions and areas for improvement, ensuring a thorough understanding of the topic.

Finally, the Extend phase encourages independent learning by assigning tasks where students explore real-world applications of Kinematics, such as its use in sports or engineering. Iqbal (2024) notes that this phase fosters critical thinking and creativity, motivating students to take an active role in their learning and further solidifying their understanding.

This structured approach, supported by the 7E's Learning Model, provides a robust framework for effective teaching and learning in Kinematics.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The initial level of learning performance in Kinematics for both the controlled and experimental groups was categorized as Did Not Meet Expectations, as reflected by their pretest scores of 67 and 68, respectively. This indicates a limited understanding of kinematics concepts prior to instruction.
2. After the intervention, the experimental group demonstrated significant improvement in their learning performance, with a posttest mean score of 83, categorized as Satisfactory, compared to the controlled group's posttest mean score of 73, which remained in the Did Not Meet Expectations category. The results confirmed that the 7E's Learning Model improved the students' comprehension and application of kinematics concepts more effectively than traditional teaching methods.
3. The experimental group exhibited a greater mean gain score (11.52) than the control group (6.6). The statistical analysis confirmed a significant difference between the two groups' performances, with the experimental group showing superior outcomes. This underscores the potential of the 7E's Learning Model as a more effective instructional approach than traditional methods.
4. The detailed lesson plan integrating the 7E's Learning Model was developed to address the least learned competencies in Kinematics, such as uniformly accelerated motion, projectile motion, and circular motion. Each phase of the model—Elicit, Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate, and Extend—was aligned with specific activities and objectives that enhanced student engagement, critical thinking, and mastery of kinematics concepts.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations of the study based on the conclusions above.

1. Senior high school physics teachers are encouraged to integrate the 7E's Learning Model into teaching practices for Kinematics and other physics topics to enhance student engagement and understanding.
2. Senior high school physics teachers are encouraged to utilize the developed lesson plan integrating the 7E's Learning Model to effectively teach kinematics

concepts, particularly uniformly accelerated motion, projectile motion, and circular motion.

3. School administrators are encouraged to promote innovative teaching strategies, such as the 7E's Learning Model, by offering training programs and providing resources to assist teachers in implementing these methods effectively.
4. Curriculum developers are encouraged to develop supplementary teaching materials, including lesson plans and activity guides, aligned with the 7E's Learning Model phases to support its implementation in classrooms.
5. Science teachers can conduct further studies on the application of the 7E's Learning Model in other STEM subjects or broader topics within physics to validate its effectiveness across different educational contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical research principles by ensuring that informed consent was obtained from all respondents before their participation. Participants were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential benefits or risks. Respondents were informed that their participation was voluntary, and they had the freedom to withdraw at any stage without facing any consequences. This measure upheld their autonomy and right to make informed decisions regarding their involvement in the research.

The study also ensured anonymity and confidentiality by not collecting personally identifiable information and keeping all responses secure and accessible only to the researcher. The respondents' well-being was prioritized by minimizing any potential risks, such as undue pressure or discomfort during participation. Additionally, no conflict of interest influenced the conduct of the study, ensuring that all research activities were conducted with integrity and objectivity.

To maintain academic integrity, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources of information were properly credited. The interpretation of findings was unbiased, ensuring that results were presented accurately and objectively. Furthermore, the study's outcomes were used purely for research purposes, contributing to the field of education without any commercial or personal gains. These ethical considerations ensured that the research was conducted responsibly, promoting credibility and reliability in its findings.

Acknowledgments

This study would not have been accomplished without numerous individuals' unwavering support, guidance, and encouragement, to whom the researcher extends his deepest gratitude. Sincere appreciation is given to Dr. Rezy V. Mendaño, Dr. Lanie M. Pacadaljen, Dr. Marife M. Lacaba, Sir Nicolas O. Boco, Jr., Sir Necasio D. Abuda, and Ma'am Emma Q. Tenedero for their invaluable expertise, patience, and mentorship throughout this endeavor. Heartfelt thanks are also extended to the EVRSHS administration, faculty, and staff for their support, as well as to the Grade 12 respondents for their cooperation and participation. Above all, the researcher offers boundless praise and gratitude to Almighty God for His wisdom, guidance, and strength, which made this study possible.

REFERENCES

- Aliyu, I., Lakpini, M. A., Abdulkarim, B., & Falalu, M. K. (2022). Effect of 7E Learning Cycle on Cell Concept Performance Among Senior Secondary School Slow Learners in Katsina Metropolis, Nigeria. *Kashere Journal of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.4314/kje.v3i1.18>
- Amin, B. D., Sahib, E. P., Harianto, Y., Patandean, A. J., Herman, H., & Sujiono, E. H. (2020). The Interpreting Ability on Science Kinematics Graphs of Senior High School Students in South Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ipa Indonesia*. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jpii.v9i2.23349>
- Ayeni, M. F. (2021). The Challenges and Prospects of Science Education Development in Africa. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.36941/mjss-2021-0033>
- Bektiarso, S. (2023). The Effect of 7E Learning Cycle Assisted by Monopoly Physics Games Toward Students' Learning Activities and Learning Outcomes in Kinetic Theory of Gases. *Jurnal Pendidikan Progresif*. <https://doi.org/10.23960/jpp.v13.i2.202329>
- Bernardo, A. B., Cordel, M. O., Calleja, M. O., M. Teves, J. M., Yap, S. A., & Chua, U. C. (2023). Profiling Low-Proficiency Science Students in the Philippines Using Machine Learning. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01705-y>
- Boller-Aying, S., & Villegas-Mendaño, R. (2024). Students' Performance on the Horizontal and Vertical Components of Projectile Motion Using Project-based Learning. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(4), 1689-1704.
- Cents-Boonstra, M., Lichtwarck-Aschoff, A., Denessen, E., Aelterman, N., & Haerens, L. (2020). Fostering student engagement with motivating teaching: an observation study of teacher and student behaviours. *Research Papers in Education*, 36(6), 754-779. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2020.1767184>
- Cordova, W., & Linaugo, J. (2022). Pedagogical Content Knowledge Practices of Public School Science Teachers. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v37i1.7584>
- Cornejo, M. (2022). Students' academic performances and least mastered skills as basis in developing learning modules for General Physics 1. *International Journal Peer Reviewed Journal Refereed Journal Indexed Journal Impact Factor SJIF*, 8(01), 2020–2021. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/E9QST>

- Dervić, D., Glamočić, D. S., Gazibegović-Busuladžić, A., & Mešić, V. (2018). Teaching physics with simulations: teacher-centered versus student-centered approaches. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 17(2), 288-299. <https://doi.org/10.33225/jbse/18.17.288>
- Hairini. (2024). The Effect of Implementing Learning Models Cycle 7e on Mathematical Problems-Solving Ability. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2024/v50i71452>
- Hidayatulloh, W., Kuswanto, H., Santoso, P. H., Susilowati, E., & Hidayatullah, Z. (2021). Exploring students' misconception in the frame of graphic and figural representation on projectile motion regarding to the covid-19 constraints. *JIPF (Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Fisika)*, 6(3), 243. <https://doi.org/10.26737/jipf.v6i3.2157>
- Iksan, Z. H., Bakar, N. A., Amirullah, A. H., & Mohd Salehudin, S. N. (2018). Understanding the Concept of Life Process in Animals Based on 7E Inquiry Model Through Lesson Study Approach. *Creative Education*. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2018.911128>
- Iqbal, M. (2024). Impact of 7E Model on Students' Academic Achievement: A Comprehensive Analysis in Educational Settings. *Journal of Education and Social Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.52223/jess.2024.5115>
- Kesteren, M. T. R. v., Krabbendam, L., & Meeter, M. (2018). Integrating educational knowledge: reactivation of prior knowledge during educational learning enhances memory integration. *NPJ Science of Learning*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41539-018-0027-8>
- Kormakova, V. N., Chernyavskikh, S. D., Satler, O. N., & Trikula, L. N. (2023). Digitalization in STEM Education: Experience of Empirical Research. *Research Result Pedagogy and Psychology of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.18413/2313-8971-2023-9-1-0-01>
- Kotvytska, K. and Ješková, Z. (2024). Study of circular and rotational motion with the help of experimentation and mathematical modeling enhanced by digital technologies. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2715(1), 012018. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2715/1/012018>
- Libata, I. A., Bin Ali, M. N., & Ismail, H. N. (2022). Constructivist Approach to Learning Activity: The Case of Junior Secondary Students' Misconception on the Three States of Matter in Basic Science, Nigeria. *Equity Journal of Science and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.4314/equijost.v8i1.2>
- Marfilinda, R., Rossa, R., & Apfani, S. (2020). The Effect Of 7E Learning Cycle Model toward Student ' s Learning Outcomes of Basic Science Concept. 3(1), 77–87.
- Maskur, R., Latifah, S., Pricilia, A., Walid, A., & Ravanis, K. (2019). The 7E Learning Cycle Approach to Understand Thermal Phenomena. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ipa Indonesia*. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jpii.v8i4.20425>
- Mbwile, B., & Ntivuguruzwa, C. (2023). Impact of Practical Work in Promoting Learning of Kinematics Graphs in Tanzanian Teachers' Training Colleges. *International Journal of Education and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.18488/61.v11i3.3343>
- Mufit, F., & Fitri, A. D. (2022). The Analysis of Experiment Video on Cognitive Conflict-Based Teaching Materials to Enhance Momentum-Impulse Concepts Understanding. *Jurnal Penelitian & Pengembangan Pendidikan Fisika*. <https://doi.org/10.21009/1.08211>
- Nizaruddin, N., Muhtarom, M., & Murtianto, Y. H. (2017). Exploring of multi mathematical representation capability in problem solving on senior high school students. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 75(6), 591-598. <https://doi.org/10.33225/17.75.591>
- Ole, F. C., & R. Gallos, M. (2021). Development and Validation of a Physics Concept Test in Kinematics for Senior High School Students. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 3(2), 95–104. <https://doi.org/10.54476/iimrj290>
- Pasju, N. F., Kristiawan, M., Sasongko, R. N., & Pancaningrum, N. (2022). The 7E Learning Cycle Model and It's Important on Cognitive Learning Outcomes of Reasoning. *Elementary Islamic Teacher Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.21043/elementary.v10i2.15108>

- Pires, E. M. S. G., Daniel-Filho, D. A., Nooijer, J. d., & Dolmans, D. (2020). Collaborative learning: elements encouraging and hindering deep approach to learning and use of elaboration strategies. *Medical Teacher*, 42(11), 1261-1269.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159x.2020.1801996>
- Rahmadani, U. (2023). Systematic Review of Misconceptions in Kinematics: Identification, Causes, and Remediation. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Ipa*.
<https://doi.org/10.29303/jppipa.v9i12.4956>
- Richner, J. (2023). The Influence of a STEM/STEAM Education Based High School on Students of the Ivoti Institute. *Sfu Educational Review*. <https://doi.org/10.21810/sfuer.v15i1.6169>
- Sadera, J. R., S. Torres, R. Y., & Rogayan, D. V. (2020). Challenges Encountered by Junior High School Students in Learning Science: Basis for Action Plan. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.082524>
- Saraç, H., & Tarhan, D. (2017). Effect of Multimedia Assisted 7E Learning Model Applications on Academic Achievement and Retention in Students. *European Journal of Educational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.6.3.299>
- Shesilya and Aloysius, S. (2023). Development of e-worksheet of coordination system in human based on learning cycle 7e to improve critical thinking ability and student motivation. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, 9(12), 11568-11575.
<https://doi.org/10.29303/jppipa.v9i12.5907>
- Sundari, P. D. (2023). Identification of Kinematics Understanding of Physics Students at the University in Coastal Area. *Bio Web of Conferences*.
<https://doi.org/10.1051/bioconf/20237905008>
- Zavala, G., Tejada, S., Barniol, P., & Beichner, R. J. (2017). Modifying the Test of Understanding Graphs in Kinematics. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.1103/physrevphyseducres.13.020111>